

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 1, No. 4; April 28, 1995

Dear Readers:

This number 4 of volume of J.UCS, the Journal of Universal Computer Science contains a selection of 5 papers from a Workshop on Hypermedia Systems held at the Graz University of Technology November 4-5, 1994. The idea to collect some of the most interesting papers into a special issue is due to John Lindsay from Kingston University, UK, who has gone through the trouble of reviewing the papers. Two further papers of this conference: "Applications and Impact of Hypermedia Systems: An Overview" (J.Lennon, H.Maurer) and "On Second Generation Hypermedia Systems" (K.Andrews, F.Kappe, H.Maurer, K.Schmaranz) have already appeared in the pilot issue of J.UCS, J.UCS 0,0 (1994).

Note that the papers present a good survey of information systems that are widespread on the Internet, starting with Gopher (authored by "Mr.Gopher" himself, Mark McCahill from Minnesota), WWW (authored by one of the four originators of WWW at CERN, Robert Cailliau), WAIS (as first full-text search engine that became widely used in connection with a variety of Internet services) to Hyper-G (a paper authored by two of the leading developers, Frank Kappe and Keith Andrews). One paper comes from an expert in the commercial arena: D. Goetze, one of the directors of Springer Pub.Co., a company known for its electronic publishing efforts including the support of this very journal J.UCS!

Hope you find this issue again interesting. Your opinion on the issues that have appeared sofar, or on J.UCS in general and how it compares to other electronic journals are much valued. Please do send me a brief note if you can spare a few moments of your time: I will report on opinions received in a later issue. For the time being, thanks for your continued interest in J.UCS. Due to the fact that we are running a number of servers, some only accessible within a particular organisation, others publicly abvailable we don't know how many readers J.UCS has got. However, our Graz J.UCS homepage has been accessed over 10.000 times by now, so a conservative estimate is that J.UCS has been looked at at least 25.000 times. This is probably quite satisfactory for a start.

With best wishes

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
email: hmaurer@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at